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CLINICAL AND BIOCHEMICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF RECURRENT RESPIRATORY TRACT INFECTIONS IN YOUNG CHILDREN IN A HOSPITAL SETTING

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Abstract: It has been established that severe RITI is associated with stress-induced changes in glycemia, decreased total protein and albumin levels, transient increases in ALT and AST activity, and significant electrolyte imbalances. Increased uric acid levels correlated with the severity of the clinical course and signs of metabolic stress. A comprehensive biochemical blood test allows for an objective assessment of the degree of metabolic maladaptation, increases the accuracy of RITI severity assessment, and supports the optimization of treatment strategies in young children in a hospital setting.

Keywords: young children; recurrent respiratory tract infections; biochemical predictors; inpatient treatment.

Recurrent respiratory tract infections in young children are a pressing pediatric problem due to their high prevalence, protracted course, and risk of repeated hospitalizations [4,8]. According to clinical observations, frequent episodes of respiratory infections in children during the first years of life are accompanied by significant metabolic changes caused by inflammation, intoxication, and drug therapy [1,6].

During acute infectious processes in young children, catabolic reactions are activated, leading to disturbances in carbohydrate and protein metabolism [11,12]. Stress-induced changes in blood glucose levels upon hospital admission reflect the activation of counter-insular mechanisms and correlate with disease severity [11,15].

Protein metabolism disorders, manifested by decreased total protein and albumin levels, are considered markers of infectious process severity and an unfavorable prognosis, especially in children with severe and protracted disease [13].

Liver function in young children with RIDP is reflected in transaminase activity (ALT and AST). Moderate transient increases in these parameters are described as a response to infectious intoxication, hypoxia, and drug exposure [1,7]. Disturbances in water and electrolyte balance (Na^+ , K^+ , Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+}) in young children develop rapidly and can be associated with dehydration, vomiting, diarrhea and infusion therapy, significantly affecting the clinical course of RIDP [6,8].

In recent years, uric acid levels have attracted the attention of researchers, being considered an integral marker of metabolic and inflammatory burden associated with the severity of the infectious process [14]. However, the role of this indicator in RITIs in young children remains poorly understood.

Objective: To study the clinical and laboratory characteristics of recurrent respiratory tract infections in young children based on blood biochemistry data.

Materials and Methods: The study included 150 children aged 1 to 3 years, hospitalized in a pediatric hospital with recurrent respiratory tract infections, with a median age of 2.1 years [1.6–2.7]. The gender distribution was relatively even, with a slight predominance of boys (54.7%). The average frequency of recurrent respiratory tract infections was 4 episodes per year, which meets the criteria for a recurrent course. Severe disease was diagnosed in 23.3% of children (Group 1), while the majority of patients (76.7%) were considered moderately severe (Group 2).

All patients underwent a comprehensive clinical and laboratory examination.

Blood biochemistry included determination of fasting and admission glucose levels, total protein and albumin, alanine aminotransferase (ALT) and aspartate aminotransferase (AST) activity, electrolyte concentrations (sodium, potassium, calcium, magnesium), and uric acid levels.

Disease severity was assessed based on clinical criteria, the presence of respiratory failure, and the need for fluid therapy.

Statistical analysis was performed using descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, and intergroup comparisons; differences were considered statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

Study results: As shown in Table 1, severe recurrent respiratory infections in young children are accompanied by statistically significant changes in biochemical parameters.

Table 1

Blood biochemical parameters in children with RITs depending on the severity of the disease

Indicator	Severe course (n=35)	Moderately severe course (n=115)	p
Blood glucose, mmol/L	5,8±0,2	5,2±0,1	<0,05
Total protein, g/L	61,4±0,6	66,8±0,5	<0,01
Albumin, g/L	34,2±0,4	38,1±0,3	<0,001
ALT, U/L	48,5±1,2	32,6±0,9	<0,001
AST, U/L	52,1±1,3	36,8±1,0	<0,001
Uric acid, μmol/L	332,4±6,8	271,6±5,4	<0,001

Patients with severe forms of the disease had higher blood glucose levels upon admission, reflecting stress-induced activation of counter-insular mechanisms during the infectious process. A significant decrease in total protein and albumin levels was also observed, indicating severe catabolism and impaired protein synthesis in the context of systemic inflammation.

Liver transaminase activity (ALT and AST) was statistically significantly higher in children with severe forms of RIDP compared to those with moderate forms, suggesting reactive liver changes due to infectious intoxication and medication

exposure. Elevated uric acid levels in this group of patients indicate increased metabolic and inflammatory stress during severe forms of the disease.

Blood electrolyte analysis (Table 2) revealed that children with severe forms of RIDP were significantly more likely to have fluid and electrolyte imbalances. In this category of patients, lower levels of sodium and potassium were recorded, which may be associated with dehydration, vomiting, diarrhea, and infusion therapy.

Table 2

Electrolyte balance indicators in children with RIDP depending on the severity of the disease

Indicator	Severe course (n=35)	Moderately severe course (n=115)	p
Sodium (Na ⁺), mmol/L	134,6±0,5	137,8±0,4	<0,01
Potassium (K ⁺), mmol/L	3,4±0,1	3,9±0,1	<0,01
Calcium (Ca ²⁺), mmol/L	2,10±0,03	2,26±0,02	<0,01
Magnesium (Mg ²⁺), mmol/L	0,68±0,02	0,82±0,02	<0,001

Decreased calcium and magnesium concentrations in children with severe disease reflect impaired electrolyte homeostasis and may exacerbate the clinical manifestations of infection, including muscle weakness, decreased exercise tolerance, and delayed recovery. These data highlight the need for dynamic electrolyte monitoring in patients with RIDP, especially in severe cases and during fluid therapy.

As shown in Table 3, children with severe RIDP had significantly more metabolic and electrolyte disturbances compared to patients with moderate disease. The most common changes were hypoalbuminemia, elevated transaminases, hyponatremia, and hypomagnesemia.

Table 3

Frequency of metabolic and electrolyte disturbances in children with RIDP

Indicator	Severe course, n (%)	Moderately severe course, n (%)	p
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Hypoalbuminemia	21 (60,0)	29 (25,2)	<0,001
Increased ALT/AST	19 (54,3)	22 (19,1)	<0,001
Hyponatremia	15 (42,9)	18 (15,7)	<0,01
Hypokalemia	13 (37,1)	14 (12,2)	<0,01
Hypomagnesemia	17 (48,6)	21 (18,3)	<0,001
Hyperuricemia	14 (40,0)	17 (14,8)	<0,01

The incidence of two or more metabolic abnormalities in patients with severe disease was more than twice as high, demonstrating the complex nature of metabolic maladaptation during severe infection. These data confirm the clinical significance of systemic biochemical assessment in risk stratification for adverse outcomes in RIDP. Table 4 demonstrates that the presence of two or more biochemical abnormalities in children with RIDP is associated with adverse clinical outcomes in hospital treatment. This category of patients had a longer febrile period, increased hospitalization time, and a higher requirement for oxygen therapy compared to children without significant metabolic abnormalities.

Table 4

Association of Biochemical Abnormalities with Clinical Outcomes in Hospital Treatment

Indicator	Duration of fever, days	Duration of treatment, bed days	Oxygen therapy, %
Normal indicators	4,3±0,2	6,5±0,3	23,1
≥2 biochemical abnormalities	5,7±0,3*	8,9±0,4*	51,8*

Note: * p<0.01 compared to the group without metabolic disorders

The obtained results indicate a close relationship between the degree of metabolic maladaptation and the effectiveness of treatment, emphasizing the prognostic value of biochemical parameters in assessing the disease course and planning treatment strategies.

Correlation analysis (Table 5) revealed statistically significant relationships between biochemical parameters and clinical characteristics of RIDP. A negative correlation was established between albumin levels and the duration of inpatient treatment, confirming the role of protein deficiency as a factor in aggravating the disease.

A positive correlation between ALT activity and the duration of the febrile period reflects the relationship between reactive liver changes and the severity of the infectious process. A negative correlation between magnesium levels and the duration of treatment indicates the influence of electrolyte disturbances on the rate of clinical recovery. An increase in uric acid levels correlated with the severity of the disease, allowing this indicator to be considered an integral marker of metabolic and inflammatory stress.

Table 5

Correlations between biochemical parameters and clinical severity

Indicators	r	p
Albumin ↔ duration of treatment	-0,42	<0,01
ALT ↔ duration of fever	0,39	<0,01
Mg ²⁺ ↔ duration of treatment	-0,41	<0,01
Uric acid ↔ severity of disease	0,44	<0,01

The results obtained indicate that the course of recurrent respiratory tract infections in young children is accompanied by complex biochemical changes reflecting the body's systemic metabolic adaptation to the infectious process. Disturbances in carbohydrate and protein metabolism, reactive changes in liver function tests, and electrolyte shifts are most pronounced in severe cases of the disease, which is consistent with data from domestic and international studies [1,4,11–13].

The identified association between uric acid levels and the severity of RITs complements current understanding of the role of metabolic markers in assessing the systemic inflammatory response in children [14].

Conclusions

1. In young children with recurrent respiratory tract infections, severe disease is accompanied by statistically significant biochemical abnormalities: increased blood glucose levels upon admission (5.8 ± 0.2 versus 5.2 ± 0.1 mmol/L; $p < 0.05$), decreased total protein (61.4 ± 0.6 versus 66.8 ± 0.5 g/L; $p < 0.01$) and albumin (34.2 ± 0.4 versus 38.1 ± 0.3 g/L; $p < 0.001$), as well as increased ALT and AST activity (48.5 ± 1.2 and 52.1 ± 1.3 U/L versus 32.6 ± 0.9 and 36.8 ± 1.0 U/L, respectively; $p < 0.001$), reflecting a pronounced metabolic load and reactive changes against the background of the infectious process.

2. Electrolyte and purine metabolism disorders in severe cases of RIDP are characterized by decreased levels of Na^+ (134.6 ± 0.5 versus 137.8 ± 0.4 mmol/l), K^+ (3.4 ± 0.1 versus 3.9 ± 0.1 mmol/l), Mg^{2+} (0.68 ± 0.02 versus 0.82 ± 0.02 mmol/l; $p < 0.01$ – 0.001) and increased concentrations of uric acid (332.4 ± 6.8 versus 271.6 ± 5.4 $\mu\text{mol/l}$; $p < 0.001$). The presence of two or more biochemical abnormalities is associated with an increase in the duration of the febrile period (5.7 ± 0.3 versus 4.3 ± 0.2 days), the duration of inpatient treatment (8.9 ± 0.4 versus 6.5 ± 0.3 bed-days) and a higher need for oxygen therapy (51.8% versus 23.1%; $p < 0.01$), which confirms the prognostic significance of a comprehensive biochemical assessment in the inpatient care of children with RIDP.

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